

Supplementary figures for “Chloroplast genome-based baraminology study of Liliales”

Matthew Cserhati

Supplementary figure 1. Elbow plot deduced from the sequence similarity matrix of the 163 species analyzed in this study.

Supplementary figure 2. Silhouette plot deduced from the sequence similarity matrix of the 163 species analyzed in this study.

Supplementary figure 3. Calinski-Harabasz plot deduced from the sequence similarity matrix of the 163 species analyzed in this study.

